

OPENING AND PREPARATION OF ORE DEPOSITS**Ibodov Jasurbek Azamat o'g'li**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7196907>

Abstract

Opening a mineral deposit is the execution of capital mining operations that open access to all or part of the mine from the surface and provide the opportunity to carry out preparatory work necessary for servicing the mine surfaces. The main goals of mineral extraction are to create transport links between parking areas (the place where minerals are extracted) and the point of receiving it on the surface, and to create conditions for the safe movement of people in mines and to provide workplaces with clean air. This article provides information on opening ore deposits and its preparation.

Keywords. Ore, mineral resources, mine, mine preparation, access road, mineral resources.

Аннотация

Вскрытие месторождения полезных ископаемых - это выполнение капитальных горных работ, открывающих доступ ко всему или части рудника с поверхности и дающих возможность провести подготовительные работы, необходимые для обслуживания поверхностей рудника. Основными целями добычи полезных ископаемых являются создание транспортных связей между стоянками (местом добычи полезных ископаемых) и пунктом их приема на поверхность, а также создание условий для безопасного передвижения людей в шахтах и обеспечение рабочих мест чистыми воздухом. В данной статье представлена информация по вскрытию месторождений руды и ее подготовке.

Ключевые слова. Руда, полезные ископаемые, рудник, подготовка рудника, подъездная дорога, полезные ископаемые.

INTRODUCTION

Capital opening works are divided into main and auxiliary types. The main ones include works with direct access to the surface: vertical and inclined shafts and shafts; assistants include intersections, crawlers and slopes. Mining methods are very diverse and differ in the nature of the main opening, their location relative to the layers or ore body, the presence of auxiliary opening and the number of underground transport horizons. The method of vertical mining depends on the

terrain, the value of the mineral, the form of its occurrence, its size and depth, the thickness and angle of deposition of layers or ore bodies, their number and the distance between them, and other factors. When choosing a cleaning method, the influence of the above geological and mining factors is taken into account. The most important of them are: minimum initial capital costs and mine construction periods; production concentration, which depends on the maximum increase in production from the stoppage; concentration of mining production in a limited number of simultaneously developed layers; shortening the length of mining operations supported by the activation of mining operations and the periodic renewal of the mining facilities of the mine by preparing new horizons or reconstructing them. At least two shafts pass (two safe exits from the mine to the surface), one to supply fresh air to the mine, and the other to vent air to the surface.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

All mineral reserves in the defined part of the mine are called geological reserves. According to the commercial value, geological reserves are divided into two groups that are considered separately: balance and off-balance. Balance reserves are reserves that satisfy industrial conditions, that is, economically useful for their development. Due to the low useful component, the low thickness of the ore body, the complexity of the conditions for their exploitation, the off-balance reserves are currently unsuitable for use, but can be considered as an object of industrial development. Delimitation of balance and off-balance reserves is carried out on the basis of the conditions established by the relevant state bodies for each mine or for a group of mines similar in geological and economic conditions.

Conditions for mineral raw materials (production conditions) are a set of requirements for the quality and quantity of minerals, mining-geological, mining engineering and other conditions for the development of deposits. Condition parameters are threshold values of physical indicators for calculating and evaluating reserves. They are organized by individual mining enterprises or associations of enterprises in accordance with the price of the extracted type of the useful component, conditions of mine development and technical equipment of the enterprise. Among other indicators, the standards provide for the minimum industrial composition of the useful component, that is, the limit at which it is economically unprofitable to extract ore and process it.

RESULTS

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Opening of the mine with vertical shafts is usually carried out on vertical (the angle of lie more than 60-70°) and sloping (the angle of lie less than 15-20°) deposits, when the increase in the length of the crossbars has less impact on the cost of opening the mine than the increase in the length of the inclined shafts. is increased. After the depth of the mine is 1000 m and more, this method becomes less appropriate due to the fact that the productivity of the skip lifting decreases when opening the mine with vertical shafts. Therefore, over the years, deep horizons are opened through inclined shafts. In this case, inclined shafts will be equipped with conveyors for transporting ore and loose rock. Inclined shafts that open lower horizons ensure the continuity of ore extraction regardless of the digging depth, the acceleration of the passage of mine lakhs, and the reduction of the period of preparation of new horizons. The most common opening method is opening through vertical shafts located on the lying side of the bed.

In the mining of very thin ore bodies, lines can be passed along the ore body, as well as along the side rocks on which the ore body lies or overhangs. The most commonly used method is to pass the streaks along the ore body. In thick deposits, the carrier lines were usually selected depending on the sides. In deposits with a high thickness, one or several streaks connected with backs are passed in the main horizon. In some cases, mainly in non-solid ores, field preparation is used, where lifting lines pass from the side of the rock.

CONCLUSION

Professors and students of higher educational institutions face many problems. The conclusion of the opinions discussed in this article is related to the need to promote a culture of creativity that encourages the flourishing of creativity among teachers and students. This is especially relevant because the priority models of professional training of teachers are deeply rooted in Uzbek culture, and educational opportunities for creative thinking are still very limited. There are few opportunities for teachers to reflect on their pedagogical practice, participate in dialogue and discuss it. Promoting an environment that promotes active learning and encourages students to use creativity in combination with other skills is a challenge for many university teachers.

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